

PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE FORMATION OF NATIONAL IDENTITY AND COMMITMENT TO SPIRITUAL VALUES IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the pedagogical and psychological features of forming a value-based attitude towards a healthy spiritual environment in students. The article also mentions the preservation of our historical and cultural heritage and its wide application in the upbringing of the younger generation.

Key words: student, healthy spiritual environment, value, youth, tradition, historical and cultural heritage, spirituality, dignity, moral purity, honesty, truthfulness, patriotism, kindness, behavior.

TALABALARDA MILLIY O‘ZLIK VA MA’NAVIY QADRIYATLARGA SADOQATNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUVLAR

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada, talabalarda sog‘lom ma‘naviy muhitga qadriyatli munosabatlarni shakllantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek maqolada, tarixiy va madaniy merosimizni saqlash hamda uni yosh avlod tarbiyasida keng qo‘llash haqida qayd etib o‘tilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: talaba, sog‘lom ma‘naviy muhit, qadriyat, yoshlar, an‘ana, tarixiy va madaniy meros, ma‘naviyat, qadr-qimmat, axloqiy poklik, halollik, rostgo‘ylik, vatanparvarlik, mehr-oqibat, xulq-atvor.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ФОРМИРОВАНИЮ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ИДЕНТИЧНОСТИ И ПРИВЕРЖЕННОСТИ ДУХОВНЫМ ЦЕННОСТЯМ У СТУДЕНТОВ

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Аннотация: В данной статье научно-теоретически проанализированы педагогико-психологические особенности формирования ценностного отношения к здоровой духовной среде у студентов. В статье также упоминается о сохранении нашего исторического и культурного наследия и его широком применении в воспитании молодого поколения.

Ключевые слова: студент, здоровая духовная среда, ценность, молодежь, традиция, историческое и культурное наследие, духовность, достоинство, нравственная чистота, честность, правдивость, патриотизм, доброта, поведение.

When considering the problem of forming a value-based attitude towards a healthy spiritual environment in students, it is necessary to emphasize that the unique way of life, thinking and worldview of our people, examples of oral folk art, the exemplary life of national heroes such as Spitamen, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, the sources that nourish our national ideology, as well as the teachings of Eastern thinkers such as Al-Khwarizmi, Al-Biruni, Farabi, Ibn Sina, Al-Bukhari, At-Termizi, Shahi Najmiddin Kubro, Ahmad Yassavi, Alisher Navoi, Ogahi about the perfect person are deep roots of the idea of national independence. [3]

So, how is the concept of a healthy spiritual environment explained? A healthy spiritual environment is a healthy-minded environment in which morality, values, mutual respect between people, harmony, and spiritual upbringing are high in society or a certain community.

When approaching from an educational and upbringing point of view, it is important to instill in the hearts of students such qualities as humanism - humane treatment of each person, respect for their rights and dignity, moral purity - adherence to such norms of behavior as honesty, truthfulness, patriotism, kindness, mutual respect and tolerance - tolerance and tolerance towards different opinions, religions, nationalities, civic responsibility - observance of laws and rules in society, having an active civic position, attention to enlightenment and education - interest and respect for science, education, reading. [1]

In the treatise, Kuronov recognizes the vice of homelessness as the most serious danger and shows the negative influence of today's "culturologists" on the upbringing of youth in the promotion of the idea of cosmopolitanism. Cosmopolitanism (from the Greek word "cosmopolites" - meaning citizen of the world) - a movement that reduces a person's love, loyalty, and protection of their native land, people, and state by considering the whole world as a single homeland. Harmful ideas such as statelessness, indifference to the present and future of the homeland, and a lack of appreciation for independence rely on and draw nourishment from cosmopolitanism."a category of people who call themselves 'citizens of the world' will be trained, and they will be instilled with the idea that in the near future there will be no borders on earth at all." [2]

Another important life factor directly influencing the formation of spirituality is closely related to the education system. [4] There is no doubt that the fundamental reforms and good deeds being implemented in our country are directly related to the spiritual education of our people, especially youth, and the level of ensuring the quality of education being organized in the continuous education system.

In the education system, the ability of young people with different views and worldviews to freely express their position and justifiably defend it plays an important role in strengthening democratic principles in society. In this process, the formation in students of a sense of awareness of a healthy spiritual environment, its value, and a sense of responsibility towards it acquires important social significance. Indeed, the younger generation, raised in an environment of common sense, mutual respect, and tolerance, will serve the sustainable and prosperous development of society in the future.

Values are usually formed through a person's emotional experiences, life experience, and perception. Each person approaches different values differently, because these values are connected with their inner world, personal needs, and worldview. For example, for one person, family can be the highest value, while for another, knowledge, freedom, or creativity are of paramount importance. This situation shows the diversity of values between people. [1]

Values directly influence a person's daily behavior, decisions, and choices. Moral norms - that is, concepts such as goodness, honesty, and loyalty - are based on values. Through values, a person determines how to live and how to interact with others. They encourage a person to be faithful to moral principles and play an important role in ensuring stability in society.

Values are often inextricably linked with the environment in which a person was raised - family, school, society, and culture. Every nation and society has its own unique system of values. These values are passed down from generation to generation and form national identity. Therefore, values that are considered important in one society may be secondary in another. Culture is considered one of the main sources of values. [5]

The formation of a value-based attitude towards a healthy spiritual environment in students is determined by the structure of social relations and types of human activity. The more diverse human activity, the richer their social relations, the clearer their attitude and worldview towards social processes.

The personal example of teachers and heads of educational institutions is one of the decisive factors in the formation and ensuring of a healthy spiritual environment. Through their every action, interaction, and humane attitude towards students, they awaken in young people an interest in high morality, kindness, and human qualities. The teacher's heartfelt words, sincere attitude, and open

communication with students have a positive impact on the spiritual environment.

In conclusion, a healthy spiritual environment is an important social environment that can be created only if every citizen, family, educational institution, and society as a whole act together. It is the foundation of the spiritual wealth and development of the people.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

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